

DELINEATION OF HOROSCOPES THROUGH DASAMSA

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Abstract:

Only a few can delineate the horoscope correctly and scientifically but practice makes man perfect. If one analyzes the same in a scientific way, the proficiency can be attained. Analysis of a horoscope is never complete without a proper study of the concerned divisional charts. Especially D10 helps us to determine the accurate prediction of a profession. So, through the Dasamsa chart (D10) one should find out the native’s Business status, profession, the position he holds and his efficiency.

Key Words: Divisional chart, Rasi, Navamsa, Dasamsa, Vargottama, Karakamsa, Atma karaka, Amatyakaraka, Karakas,

Divisional Charts:

The following points should be remembered while studying a divisional chart

- A planet occupying benefic signs in divisional charts becomes powerful. Suppose Jupiter is in Sagittarius in Navamsa and Capricorn in Dasamsa. This shows that Jupiter period will be good for marital matters, relationship etc. and a difficult one for professional matters. Thus a planet depending upon its position in divisional charts gives different areas of native’s life.
- A planet occupying the same sign in
- Rasi chart and a divisional chart becomes very powerful (Vargottama). Here it should not be debilitated or in the 1st or 30th degree. In both these conditions despite being Vargottama the planet remains weak.
- The divisional charts should always be studied along with the natal horoscope and never separately. Suppose the ascendant is Virgo with 3rd and 8th lord Mars in 2nd house at 11°. Here, despite being exalted in Dasamsa, Mars will give financial difficulties as in Rasi chart it is 3rd and 8th lord in the house of wealth.
- When studying a divisional chart see the following – a). Ascendant lord of the divisional chart b). Lord of the particular house, e.g., in Navamsa the lord of the 7th house and also the position of 8th lord of the Rasi charts. c). Planets occupying the concerned house in Rasi chart. See their position in the divisional chart. Suppose you are studying Dasamsa. For planets in Rasi chart in the 10th house. Study their position in Dasamsa charts. d). Natural significator. e). See the position of dasa and sub period lords.
- See the planets connected with a particular house in Rasi chart whether by lordship or position. Their sign position in the Navamsa chart should be analyzed. Other planets are not very important while studying a Navamsa chart.
- It should be remembered that exaltation or debilitation in divisional charts does not ensure a favorable or unfavorable event respectively. For example

	Dasamsa –D10		
			Asc
			Ven

Here Venus is the 10th lord and is debilitated. But it will still give career betterment in the form of some financial gains because it is the 10th lord in the 2nd house. This is the proper way to study a horoscope and a divisional chart. How to predict profession through Dasamsa?

To predict the profession of a native we should analyze the following divisional charts.

- The Rasi. D1
- The Navamsa. D9
- Dasamsa D10
- Yogas present in the charts.
- The Main and Sub – periods of the native.

The Sign – D1 – The planet's connection between 10th house, 11 house and the ascendant to be considered for the prediction of profession. Same way planets are positioned to be seen also from the Moon ascendant. Navamsa – D9 – The strength of the planets in the Rasi chakra can be seen from this divisional chart D9 – Navamsa. The strength of 10th lord in Rasi can be seen in Navamsa by its position in that division. If a planet is exalted in rasi and is debilitated or in the dhur sthanas (6, 8 or 12) in navamsa, will confer only malefic

effects. If it is reversed, say debilitated in rasi and exalted in D9, we can expect benefic results. The Planet in varkotham (i.e. planet placed in the same rasi in Rasi and in the Navamsa) position will give good results.

Karakamsa ascendant- The planet in the highest degree in rasi chakra is considered as Atmakaraka. The sign where Athmakaraka is placed in the Navamsa is known as Karakamsa. The planets connected to the 10th house from this Karakamsa will determine the profession of the native. There are 108 nakshatra padas in 12 Signs. In each sign two padas are considered as Pushkara navamsa, the planet or lagna position fall in this Pushkara navamsa confer benefic results. Dasamsa – D10 – The extended position of karma bava (10th house) is called Dasamsa – D – 10. The ascendant of Dasamsa is very much important to judge about the profession of the native. The other places to determine the same are Artha Trines (2, 6, and 10) and the 7th house. (2nd house – money, 6th house – Service, 10th house – pride through profession, 7th house – 10 house from 10th) The karaka planets of 10th house –The Sun, Mercury, Jupiter and Saturn and their position in D10 - are also very much important to determine the profession of the native. D1 – Rasi chart is the prime factor. D10 should be analyzed comparatively.

	D1 - Rasi		
		Mars	Asc

The planet Mars is exalted in both the divisional charts D9 and D10 (Navamsa and Dasamsa) as such the native will get benefic results. He may become an industrialist. He may have his own business or higher position in his Job. But in Rasi chakra Mars being the 3rd and 8th lord for Virgo ascendant gives malefic effects and is placed in Dhana bhava. So, Mars in his Main dasa and sub periods, give only bad effects as such, ups and downs in business, transfer in Job and many other unwanted problems to the native. So, all other divisional charts should be compared with D1 – Rasi chakra for the delineation of an individual chart. Dasamsa – Starting from the same sign for odd sign and from the 9th with reference to an even sign, the 10 Dasamsas each of 3 are reckoned. These are presided over by ten rulers of the cardinal directions viz. Indra, Agni, Yama, Rakshasa, Varuna, Vayu, Kubera, Isana, Brahma and Anantha in case of an odd sign. It is in the reverse order that these presiding deities are reckoned when an even sign is given.

The Karakas –

The Sun – confer Power and prestige

Jupiter – Gives growth in Business or in service.

Mercury – confer financial growth.

Saturn – helps to do all hard work.

Weather Service or business. Which one is better?

6th house denotes Service, 7th house denotes business. In Dasamsa chakra if 6th house and 6th lord are strong the native will succeed in his service. If one of these is weak, service will be obstructed.

In Dasamsa chakra if 7th house and 7th lord are strong the native will succeed in his business. If one of these is weak there will be obstructions in business.

A strong 6th lord, 7th lord or the planets connected to 10th house will determine the field in which the native will be famous and an expert. The correlation between 6th, 7th houses to 10th house makes the native to do both service and business in their career.

Owner or Servant –

The owner of the firm is indicated by the 9th house and the servant or worker of that place is indicated by 5th house. If a malefic planet aspect or combine with 9th house, the owner of the firm will be desperate and depraved. A beneficial combination makes the owner a good man and helpful to his subordinates. The 9th house also represents father and elder brother. 5th house represents progeny. The benefic combination confers the native with a good and obedient servant or worker.

How to read D10 – Dasamsa?

- The ascendant in the dasamsa represents the native. 6th house shows the service and the 10th represents the professional improvement and the growth. The lords of the, 3rd houses of the above said houses, i.e.- 8th, 12th house, confer bad results during their main and sub-periods. 8th house represents – retirement and the 3rd house shows the short leave taken by the native.
- The native will have a desire to be the boss of his concern, If the ascendant lord is placed in the 9th house. So, the native can start his own business. The 2nd house represents the investment capital. The Kendra sthanas to the second house i.e. 5th, 8 and 11th houses represents the investments through partners of the firm (5th), by getting loans from financial institutions (8th) and by his own investment (11th) respectively.
- When the Dragon’s head (Rahu) occupies Dasamsa lagna, there will be frequent changes in the native’s career with ups and downs in income.

- If the combination of the Sun and Saturn exist in the D10 – Dasamsa 6th house or in 10th house the native may have unwanted quarrels with his superiors or unstable progress in profession.
- Gains in business, promotions in the Job can be expected when the main and sub-periods of the planets in the Kendra's of D10-Dasamsa. In the trikona lords main and sub-period will confer help from elders and friends.
- The 10th house or lord is connected to the planet Saturn in D10- dasamsa, the native will not have a proper job or permanent job. There may be problems and difficulties during the main and sub-periods of the weak planets or watery planets in the 10th house.
- In D10- Dasamsa the planets Mars or Saturn or other malefic planets, get connected with the 10th house or 10th lord, the native will be blamed and get a bad name in his business.

Yogas – All Yogas in its main and sub-periods keep the native in a good position. The native who has more sub yogas in his chart succeeds in his life. On the other hand, if Ava yogas are strong it stops the progress in his life.

The important yogas –

Dharma – Karmathipathi Yoga – 9th house (house of Dharma) or its lord, 10th house (house of Karma) or its lord combine to confer these Yoghas.

Raj Yoga

Dhan yoga

Raja sambandha yoga

Pancha maha Purusha Yogas like

Ruchaka Yoga

Bhadra Yoga

Hamsa Yoga

Sasa Yoga and Graha malika Yoga.

What type of profession, the native will get?

10th house and planets occupy and D10 – Dasamsa are to be examined for finding the profession of the native. There are hundreds of karakaththuvras in the Rasi Chakra. To know different amsaas of our life, Sage Parashara has given shodasa vargas (16 vargas). For profession we should follow D10- Dasamsa in the following ways –

- The professions indicated by the planets connected to Artha Thirikonaas 2, 6, and 10th houses of D10 – Dasamsa.
- The professions indicated by 10th house in Rasi chakra.D1.
- The profession indicated by the 10th house from Karakamsa in Navamsa.D9.
- The profession is indicated by the Amatyakaraka position in Rasi chakra and Dasamsa.

If all the professions indicated by all the above said points are the same profession, then no problem. If these are different, the native will start the profession indicated by the main and sub – periods of the planets in the Artha trikona (Trine) and will do some other job. So, the astrologer should carefully analyze the chart for the proper profession. The 10th house from 10th house to the 7th house also helps to find out the profession.

Now, we will see the professions signified by the 9 planets.

The Sun – The Sun denotes government service, trees, timber, chanting of hymen , gambling, wool, circus, politics, medicine, metal work, gold, father, kings, fire arms, fire, poisons and forests. He may be employed in State service, administration or in management. It indicates people having much authority and power. He gets income and gains through one's father. Medical profession is possible. Embassy, trade in pearl and gold. Western astrologers attribute the following professions to the Sun. All positions of trust and authority, prominent positions in government, commanders, bankers, noblemen, kings, emperors, goldsmiths etc.

The Moon – mind, liquid, sea travel, liquor shop, milk sale, milk products, nurse, servant maid, hotel, restaurant, supplying food products, bakery, poet etc. agriculture, corals, pearls, garments, cows, sugar, shipping, Navy and water supply, selling rice and food stuffs. Mars – fire related works, technical, cooking, metallurgy, gun, bullet, armor, army, uniformed service, hardware, boxer, sportsmen, Surgeon, techno crafts, theft, burglary, sin, crime, injury, blood, gold, copper, gases, engineers, dentists, butchers, chemists, druggists, electrical works etc.

Mercury – library, writer, publisher, printers, documentation, professor, accountant, clerk, business, trader, telephone, wireless communication, media, messenger, radio, television, learning new languages, translation, news paper, wooden works, learning, arts, sculpture, medical profession, expertise, minister ship, wit, cleverness, astrology, wisdom, chanting Vedas, priesthood, literature, poetry, scriptures, orators, advocate, auditor, agent, import-export etc. Jupiter – governs religion, duties, legal affairs, devotion, good fortune, and wealth, worship of deities, Brahmins, teaching, puranas, scriptures, Vedas and correct conduct. Advisors, grocery shop, tobacco, sweets, treasury, plastic, advocate, judge etc.

Venus – poet, artist, cinema, drama, devotional singers, entertainments, beautician, fragrance, makeup materials, fashion designer, decoration materials, coffee and tea leaves, drawing, photography, and cartoon.

Garlands, jewels, marriage, perfumes, ornaments, music, painters, singers, artist of all kinds, poet etc. Saturn –

coal, petrol, metals, scavenger, real-estate, building contractor, mortuary, burial ground job, lead, iron, grains, lazy people, servants, lowly people, poor man, renunciation, plumbers, watchman, hard labor, ice, ice box, refrigeration, coffin maker etc.

Dragon’s head – Rahu – hunting, low jobs, service, degraded acts, exile, theft, magic, sorcery, humorous acts, inventions, litigations, science, aerial navigation, psychology, metaphysical studies, violence, accidents, import, secret associations, spy, murder, crime, mines, poisonous drugs, production of machineries and sales etc. Dragon’s tail – Ketu – producer of wisdom, religious knowledge, spiritual studies, knowledge leading final emancipation, export, spiritual leaders, occult sciences, philosophy, corn, small machinery, terrorist, conspirator, ivory, bone etc. One of the important rules in Dasamsa:- Debilitated planets in Dasamsa confer best results. It gives the result of that house where it gets debilitated. Rules to analyze Dasamsa chart:-

- Dasamsa Ascendant lord.
- Planets in Dasamsa Ascendant.
- Planets aspect Dasamsa Asc. / Asc. Lord.
- 10th lord
- Planets in 10th lord.
- Planets aspect Dasamsa 10th house / 10th Lord.

In the main and sub-periods of the above said planets the native will do that profession, denoted by these planets. In the main and sub periods of the planets in Kendra, planets in 4th or 10 houses, when connected to Asc. Lord or 10th lord the native will get the best results in this period. Same is the case of the planets in Trine. The planets in 6-8-12th houses from Dasa lord and in that planet’s dasa, bhukti period, the native will have a lot of problems in his profession. The planets in 6-8-12th houses from Dasamsa Asc, do not aspect the Asc. Lord or 10th lord, in that dasa, bhukti period, and the native will have a lot of problems in his profession.

The planet, which get the aspect or connection of Asc. Lord, though it is not in a strong position in the Rasi chakra D1, there will be good improvement in his profession. The type of profession depends upon the Rasi in which Dasamsa lagna falls. If the Asc. Lord is in its exalted or moolatrikona rasi or aspect of Asc.lord or 10th lord in Dasamsa lagna, the result will be fine and good things will happen in their profession. The connection of Dur sthanaas will confer bad effects. With the above rules if we are unable to find the proper profession, then we must see the planet which aspect 10th lord or 10th house, whichever is strong and come to a conclusion. If Dasamsa lagna or the lord get the connection of the same planet, the native will carry out the same profession throughout his life. To understand the above facts we will analyze the following few horoscopes.

Case Study 1:

This is the horoscope of former Election Commissioner Sri. T. N. Seshan.
 Sri. T. N. Seshan, 4 – 5 – 1933, 3-30 AM, Palghat, Kerala

Asc	Mer Sun	Ve					
Ra	Rasi D1				Ve	Navamsa.D9	Ma, Sat Ke
Sat				Ke, Ma Ju		Ra	
Mo				Su	Asc,Mo	Ju	

	Asc,Sat	Ra	
Ju,Ve	Dasamsa. D10		
Su			Mo, Me
Ma	Ke		

Acs-16 – 26 – The SUN – 29 -49 (Athma Karak)
 The Moon – 26 – 54 (Amatyakaraka), Mars – 13 – 15.
 Mercury – 13 – 28, Jupiter – 20 – 22.
 Venus – 05 – 35, Saturn – 23 – 18.
 Rahu – 10 – 56.

Rasi – D1 – The pisces is the ascendant. The Ascendant lord and the 10th lord Jupiter is in the 6th house (Service). The 5th lord Moon is also in 10th which confer Raja Yoga. 10th lord Jupiter aspect 10th house, thus 10th house becomes strong. As the 2nd and 9th lord Mars conjunct with Jupiter, it becomes stronger. Navamsa – D9 – The 10th lord in Rasi is in the 12th house of Navamsa. The 10th lord the Sun is in the 2nd house and with the aspect of lagna lord Mars. (2, 6, 10). As the lagna lord and the 9th lord are in “Parivarthan Yoga, the lagna lord Mars gets “Necha Pangha”. (The Sun, Jup, Mer) Mercury is in 10th house and the 10th lord is in 2nd house. Dasamsa – D10 – He became famous because the 10th lord is in lagna. The lagna lord Mars is in Jupiter’s house, (bhagya bhava). 10th lord Saturn aspect his own house (Karma Bhava) (Saturn – the Sun - Mars). Yogha:- In

Rasi D1 – The 10th lord Jupiter and 9th lord Mars are in 6th house and confer Dharma karma athipathi Yog. The Jupiter, Mars combination in 6th house, forms Lakshmi Yoga. Navamsa – D9 – He served independently and became famous, because the 10th lord Saturn is in Navamsa Lagna. He was praised by all.

The Sun is an important planet in Rasi – Navamsa – and Dasamsa. So, he was in a Government Job. He was an intellectual because of Jupiter. The Saturn made him a hard worker. In Dasamsa as Mars is prominent he was courageous. He was like lion to all politicians. In Dasamsa, there is no planet. Neecha Saturn aspect 7th house. As mentioned earlier debilitated planets confer good results, in the year 1991, in the dasa of Saturn he became the chief election commissioner of our nation. As Saturn aspect the Sun (enemies) he makes all the politicians run. He made many reforms in the election commission. As the 6th lord Mercury is in 5th house Dasamsa, in Saturn Dasa, Mercury Bukthi, (1994) government appointed two more election commissioners to suppress his power. He was religious-minded because of strong Jupiter both in Rasi and Dasamsa. He was more powerful because the Amaithiya Karaka Moon was in the 10th house in Rasi, in the 5th house of Dasamsa, and in the Ascendant of Navamsa. So, all the reforms he made were appreciated by the public.

Raja Yoga is formed in the younger age when Yoga planets are in the 2nd, 4th, 10th and 8th houses. If it is in 8th, 7th, and 9th the yoga is formed in the old age and if it is in other houses it happens in Middle age. So, he was lucky in his middle age. In Dasamsa Ketu is in 8th house. So, in Saturn dasa Ketu Bukthi (March, 1997 to April, 1998) after facing a lot of problems, he retired from service. In rasi the exalted Atmakaraka the Sun is very Strong. In Navamsa the karakamsa lord Jupiter is placed in the 11th to Sagittarius. In Dasamsa the Sun is in 10th house and has directional strength.

Case Study 2:

Horoscope of a chartered accountant and an exporter

Ra		Asc//		Me			
Ju	Rasi-D1		Mo		Navamsa – D9		Ra
				Ke			Asc//
Ma	Me, Ve, Su		Sat, ke	Ve	Su, Ju, Ma		Mo

	Ju, Me	Mo, Ke	
	Dasamsa – D10		Sat
			Asc// Ma
Ve	Su, Ra		

Asc – 25.42. Mars – 24. 32 Sat – 08 - 02
 Sun – 13-33 Mer – 28 . 42 Rahu – 01 - 20
 Moon- 07.04 Ven – 17 – 23

Birth Star – Poosam - Athma karak – Mercury. Amathiya Karak – Mars.

Dasa Balance – 13 Y – 08 M – 07 Days.

Rasi – D1 – 10th lord Saturn is in Yogakaraka Mercury. Mercury is with the chaturtha Kendra lord the Sun. (Venus, Jupiter, Saturn).

Dasamsa – D10 – Ascendant lord the Sun is at an angle with Dragon’s head. 10th lord Venus in Jupiter’s house. The Jupiter aspect Venus. 12th lord the Moon is exalted. The Ascendant lord aspect on 10th house. The combination of Jupiter, Venus, and Mercury denote the profession of a chartered accountant. Mercury signifies Accounts, Venus – money matters. There is no planet in the 7th house. The Mars aspect of the 7th house. 7th house lord Saturn shows foreign contact. Ketu is with the 12th lord the Moon. So, the native is doing export business. 6th lord in 12th confers viparita Raja yoga. In Rasi, Navamsa and Dasamsa the Sun is in Scorpio sign as saphama and chaturtha kendras . As such the Sun is very strong. In Dasamsa Saturn the 6th and 7th lord is in 12th house and the depositor the Moon is in 10th house with Ketu. These combinations confer the native the profession of chartered accountant and he also started export business too. He took over the export business from his elder brother, after the death of his brother. This happened because of the 11th lord in 10th house and of Viparitha Raja yoga.

Case Study 3:

The horoscope of an Advocate.

15 – 01- 1928. Time of birth – 01 – 24 AM.

JU		Ra		Asc//			
	Rasi – D1			Mo	Dasamsa – D10		
Su, Me				Sat			
Ma	Sat, Ke, Ve	Asc//	Mo	Ma	Ve		
				Ju		Me	Su, Ra

Rasi – D1 – The planets Jupiter, Saturn denotes Law. Jupiter is in his own house and that 6th house shows disputes. Saturn is in 2nd house with lagna lord Venus. Jupiter Aspect the 2nd house (Saturn). The 10th lord, the Moon, is in the 12th house. (Punishment). The 6th house lord Jupiter aspect the Moon and confer Guru-Chandra Yogha. The Sun and Mercury aspect 10th house. Dasamsa – D10 – The Ascendant is Pisces. The 10th lord and the lagna lord Jupiter is in its moola trikona Rasi. The 6th lord (disputes) the Sun and Rahu aspect the Ascendant. As 10th lord Jupiter is strong, during his main period he was a best and famous advocate (upto 27-7-1965) .

Though Mars has no connection with lagna and lagna lord, Mars is the lord of 2nd and 9th and exalted in the 11th house. So, he earned plenty of money in his advocate profession. During Saturn's main period he suffered a lot because of his health and with the help of doctors he continued to do his profession. This was possible because of the position of the exalted Mars who is the 10th lord from the position of Saturn. Mercury is in 8th house. 8th house denotes retirement. As Rahu is in the 12th house to Mercury, in Mercury's main period and Rahu sub-period his profession came to an end.

Case Study 4:

This horoscope is of a Medical professor. D.O.B - 01-10 -1953 – 05 – 39 PM

Asc//			Ju	Ra		Su	
	Rasi –D1		Mo Ke	Navamsa – D9			
Ra			Ma, Ve			Mo Ve	
		Me, Sat	Su	ASc// Sat		Me, Ju	Ma Ke

Asc//	Mo	Ke	Ju
Ma, Ve	Dasamsa – D10		
	Sat, Ra	Me	Su

Asc – 13-25 Sun – 14 – 50 The Moon – 03 – 34
 Mars – 17 – 23. Mercury – 02 – 07 JU – 02- 59
 Ve – 15 – 46. Saturn – 04 – 03 Rahu – 07 – 40
 Dasa Balance – Saturn – 18 Y – 08 M – 01 Day.

Rasi – D1 – As the 10th lord Jupiter aspect the 10th house becomes strong. The Karmakaraka Saturn is also aspect 10th house. 5th lord the Moon is in his own house. Saturn is exalted. From the 4th house to 8th house planets occupy and form Graha malika Yoga. Ascendant lord aspect the 8th and 12 houses.(ill health and hospital). Navamsa – D9 – Jupiter is in 12th (Hospital) house. Here from 10th house lagna Graha malika Yoga is formed. The Moon and Venus are in 10th house. Venus and the Sun are in Parivartan Yoga.(7th house & 10th house). Dasamsa – D10 – Ascendant lord Jupiter in the house of education 4. Mercury is in 8th house, which is Venus' house. The Medical signification lord the Sun is in 7th house. As the Jupiter aspect 10th house, so he became a medical professor.

9th house denotes teaching job. 9th lord exalted Mars in the 11th house. The planet Mars aspect the 6th house. The 10th lord Jupiter also aspects the 12th house. 6th house denotes ill health and 12th house represents the hospital. Thus he became a medical professor. 10th lord Jupiter in the 4th house and aspect Mercury. The 11th and 12th lord Saturn is in his exalted house. The aspect of 10th lord also is on him. So, Saturn is strong. The 11th and 12th lord Saturn and 2nd and 9th lord Mars are in mutual transfer. As the 2, 9 and 11th connection confer excellent income through medical professor Job and by private practice. Saturn, Rahu denotes medicine. The 11th lord is exalted in Rasi and the 9th lord in Dasamsa. Venus is in varkkotham position. In Rasi he is in 6th house. In Navamsa he is in 10th house. (2,6,10). In Dasamsa the exalted bagya lord is in 11th house, house of gain. So, as a professor he earned plenty of money.

Conclusion:

Many astrologers finish their predictions only with Rasi chakra. Ancient rishis have introduced different types of Divisional charts to get the accurate predictions of the native. All astrologers should try these divisional charts for accurate predictions.

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